

2023

RADx-UP Community Collaboration Grant Program Evaluation

End of Year Report

RADx-UP Tracking & Evaluation Team

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Abbreviations

CCPH	Campus Community Partners for Health
CDCC	Coordination and Data Collection Center
CHER	UNC Center for Health Equity Research
C ₂ G	Community Collaboration Grant
DA	Data Analytics
DEI	Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion
EO	Evaluation Objective
EQ	Evaluation Question
MSC	Most Significant Change
NIH	National Institutes of Health
PI	Principal Investigator
RADx-UP	Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations
SEBI	Social, Ethical, and Behavioral Implications
SECDP	Stakeholder Engagement, Communication, and Dissemination Plan
SEP	Strategic Evaluation Plan
T&E	Tracking & Evaluation
UNC	The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
US	United States

Executive Summary

This 2023 end of year evaluation report details the RADx-UP Community Collaboration Grant (C₂G) key evaluation findings. The RADx-UP-C₂G awards up to \$50,000 to support community partners to help advance capacity, training, support, and community experience with COVID-19 testing initiatives for underserved populations, as defined by the NIH¹. Community-serving organizations, faith-based organizations, community-based clinics, and tribal nations and organizations are eligible to apply for funding for the C₂G program¹.

The Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill (UNC) collected multiple cross-sectional surveys over the project period and utilized a mixed-methods approach to evaluate the C₂G program, collecting data on project updates, activities, outcomes, and CDCC support and resources used by the awardees at a minimum of three time points for cycles 1 to 6 (see [Appendix 1 for the RADx-UP C₂G Evaluation Logic Model](#)).

This report explicitly covers the evaluation of **the C₂G** projects from January 1, 2022, through January 5, 2024. It presents data from project cycles 1-6 as there was no data for cycle 7 at the time of the report. It covers survey responses from 55 projects and in-depth interviews from 31 projects.

The purpose of this report is two-fold: 1) describe key evaluation findings that indicate **RADx-UP C₂G program** outputs, outcomes, productivity, and impact; 2) describe the stakeholder-engaged process of establishing evaluation feedback loops for identifying and addressing areas of improvement.

Key Findings from Evaluation

- C₂G funded projects throughout the US, with the [majority located in the Southern and Northeastern regions](#).
- C₂G projects engaged their communities in COVID-19 testing (79%), generated, and disseminated communication materials, and provided training and education around COVID-19, all of which were the most common project activities.
- Overall, 85% (n=49/55) of projects reported that they were satisfied with RADx-UP CDCC administration's support. [Similarly, 85% of projects were satisfied with the C₂G administration team's communication \(n=48/55\), use of communication channels \(n=52/55\), dissemination of information\(n=51/55\) and adaptations to meet needs \(n=48/55\).](#)
- Despite satisfaction, projects reported ways to improve CDCC resources in interviews, such as [simplifying the application process, increasing flexibility in some of the grant requirements, supporting collaboration among projects, and making localized and/or more culturally relevant information available.](#)
- Projects reported that the most common ongoing challenges for pilot projects included [administrative, outreach, and staffing challenges](#). Suggested improvements to

administrative support included simplifying the application process and increasing flexibility in grant requirements.

These findings are detailed throughout this report.

Conclusion

The C₂G projects improved access to and uptake of COVID-19 testing in diverse populations including underserved and vulnerable populations. Projects reported activities mostly around developing culturally appropriate COVID-19 testing materials, and training and education. They also emphasized the need to engage community members in implementation strategies. Engaging the community is pivotal in project awareness and implementation, especially for these short duration projects. Through engagement, projects can develop sustainable research infrastructure and increase community capacity for future research.

I. Overview of the C₂G Program

The Community Collaboration Grant program (C₂G) was part of the larger Rapid Acceleration of Diagnostics - Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) program which aims to ensure that all Americans, particularly those from underserved and vulnerable communities most affected by COVID-19, had access to COVID-19 testing to reduce the disparities in COVID-19-associated morbidity and mortality.

The C₂G Program sought to achieve the goals of the larger RADx-UP program through¹:

- Removing barriers to COVID-19 testing in underserved communities through communication, outreach, and training
- Improving COVID-19 testing uptake, COVID-19 diagnosis, and test reporting
- Providing training and education for community members around COVID-19 testing topics of interest
- Generating culturally appropriate communication materials related to COVID-19 testing.

The RADx-UP Coordination and Data Collection Center (CDCC) supported RADx-UP projects as they served their communities. The CDCC served as the technical support system and infrastructure to maximize the impact and effectiveness of all projects within the RADx-UP program. The Duke Clinical Research Institute (DCRI) and the Center for Health Equity Research (CHER) at the University of North Carolina (UNC), Chapel Hill, oversaw the CDCC.

Overview of the RADx-UP C₂G Evaluation

The Tracking and Evaluation (T&E) team at the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill (UNC), comprehensively assessed the C₂G program's productivity and impact by evaluating its projects. Evaluation findings have been used by the C₂G team to assist awardees and to

improve CDCC support and overall understanding of each project’s progress toward reaching their intended goals.

The T&E team employed the core components of the **Translational Science Benefits (TSBM) Model**² to assess the translation of innovation related to COVID-19 testing into clinical applications, healthcare guidelines, community interventions, policies, and other outcomes that benefit C₂G underserved communities at large. The team employed the **Reach Effectiveness Adoption Implementation Maintenance (RE-AIM) Framework** to address individual- and organization-level impacts to measure the sustainability and effectiveness of C₂G programs^{3,4}. The RE-AIM components were used to evaluate the wide reach, sustainable adoption, implementation processes, and long-term effects of the C₂G program. The team also employed the **Most Significant Change (MSC) approach** to better understand C₂G program outcomes and the values held by different stakeholders⁵.

The RADx-UP C₂G Program Evaluation Objectives included assessing:

1. The extent to which the C₂G Program improved access to and uptake of COVID-19 testing in underserved populations and COVID-19 medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable populations.
2. C₂G program support of community partners to help advance COVID-19 testing capacity, training, support, and community experience.
3. The extent to which the C₂G program increased training, education, communication, information dissemination, and capacity building related to COVID-19 testing, isolation, and contact tracing in communities.
4. How the C₂G program maximize the impact, effectiveness, and efficiency of RADx-UP CDCC.

An overview of the RADx-UP C₂G aims, outcomes, and associated evaluation key measures are available in **Table 1**.

Table 1. Overview of RADx-UP C₂G Aims, Outcomes, and Associated Evaluation Key Measures

Overview of Outcomes and Key Measures		
Outcomes	Measures	Evaluation Tools Used
C ₂ G Aim 1: Improve access to and uptake of diagnostic COVID-19 testing in underserved populations and COVID-19 medically, geographically, and socially vulnerable populations		
Increase in individuals reached with testing services or information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of individuals reached through project activities (dependent on project type and activity; will not be available in all cases) • Type of NIH-designated underserved populations and COVID-19 vulnerable populations targeted through projects (per cycle and cumulatively) 	6- and 12-month evaluation surveys

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity of populations reached (geographically, across underserved and vulnerable population categories) 	
C ₂ G Aim 2: Support community partners to help advance capacity, training, support, and community experience with COVID-19 testing initiatives		
<p>Collaborations established between C₂G awardees and other NIH-supported COVID-19 initiatives</p> <p>Expanded RADx-UP Resource Library</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diversity of organizations funded (location, organization type) # of communities of practice established between C₂G and RADx-UP awardees # of collaborations between C₂G awardees and CEAL programs # of new materials/resources added to Resource Library 	6- and 12-month evaluation surveys; 18-month interviews
C ₂ G Aim 3: Increase training, education, communication, information dissemination, and capacity building related to COVID-19 testing, isolation, and contact tracing in communities.		
<p>Educational materials developed and disseminated</p> <p>Community personnel training or workshops held</p> <p>Transportation or other testing-related support services provided</p> <p>Enhanced data collection and surveillance of COVID-19 testing activities supported</p> <p>Effective strategies for communication of COVID-19 test results created</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # of training or educational events # of educational materials developed Types of communications disseminated (PSAs, social media blasts, ads on buses, etc.) Types of direct community support projects provide (Transportation services, referrals, etc.) Strategies to communicate test results/other follow-up measures # of projects facilitating testing 	6- and 12-month evaluation surveys; 18-month interviews
C ₂ G Aim 4: Implement a C ₂ G program to maximize the impact, effectiveness, and efficiency of RADx-UP CDCC		
<p>Recruitment of a sufficient number of applicants</p> <p>Timely launch of projects</p> <p>Timely completion of projects</p> <p>Feedback on utility and quality support</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # of applicants per cycle # of projects awarded per cycle # of days between award notification and first invoice Utilization of RADx-UP resources and support % of awardees that expended funding in a 12-month grant period Types of CDCC support used Suggested improvements to CDCC support/resources 	<p>C₂G Program Records</p> <p>6- and 12-month evaluation surveys; 18-month interviews</p>

II. Methods

Data Sources

The evaluation of RADx-UP C₂G consisted of a cross-sectional evaluation study design, which involves collecting data from most C₂G program awardees at three time points (6, 12, and 18 months). Data collection included gathering data on project updates, activities, outcomes, and use of CDCC support and resources (see [Appendix 1 for the RADx-UP C₂G Evaluation Logic Model](#)). See [figure 1](#) for a flow diagram of how the data sources map onto program evaluation.

C₂G Program Records

The C₂G grant administration leadership team provided grant administration data, such as the number of applicants per cycle, to the T&E team.

Six and 12-month Survey

The 6-month interim and 12-month closeout progress reports surveys (herein referred to as the 6-month and 12-month evaluation surveys) were distributed by the T&E team through REDCap to C₂G projects based upon project start dates. Evaluation surveys collected a combination of qualitative and quantitative data to assess progress on project activities, information on collaborations, populations engaged, project roadblocks, and the usefulness of CDCC support. Items on these evaluation surveys also assessed outcomes and SBM Framework indicators. Survey questions aligned with project requirements and expectations as outlined in the request for application (RFA).

Figure 1. Evaluation Data Sources

Follow-up Interview (18 months)

At 18 months from their start dates (six months post-project), most C₂G projects were asked to participate in interviews conducted remotely by Zoom with the T&E team to assess longer-term impacts of the projects. Topics include any sustained project activities and other achievements that stemmed from the pilot project (additional external funding, new partnerships, etc.). This is also where significant change (SC) stories were collected³. All projects were assigned an unidentified number to protect projects' confidentiality, and those

numbers are reported throughout this document. One cycle 1 project, five cycle 4 projects, four cycle 5 projects and all cycle 6 projects did not complete an 18-month interview.

Data Analysis. The data was analyzed and visualized using Microsoft Power BI, a data visualization software. Results were shared with the C₂G leadership as dashboard reports which are reports that provide a visual summary of data findings. The following products are developed from the analysis of data sources.

Six and 12-Month Aggregate Dashboards

The 6- and 12-month survey results were descriptively analyzed and summarized by funding award cycle in aggregate dashboards. Data in these dashboard reports included:

- The number and type of projects reporting
- The number and type of partner organizations
- Types of communities served
- Project activities
- CDCC support services used
- Satisfaction with CDCC support services
- Ongoing and resolved challenges

These results were used by the C₂G implementation team and projects to facilitate any needed updates to the evaluation plan and improvements to the program overall. Open-ended response items were coded as categorical variables and include challenges and roadblocks projects have encountered- both resolved and ongoing.

Biannual T&E Evaluation Reports

Six and 12-month surveys were analyzed across projects and descriptively summarized cumulatively in biannual T&E evaluation reports. Open-ended response items were coded as categorical variables. Qualitative data included questions about ongoing and resolved project challenges and roadblocks. Other qualitative data included questions that ask about improvements to RADx-UP CDCC support or resources.

Project Impact Profiles. Six-month and 12-month evaluation survey data were also used to create Translational Science Benefits (TSB) model project impact profiles⁵. The C₂G implementation and the T&E teams co-developed each project's profile with the respective project. The profiles provide a high-level description of how project outcomes reported on the 12-month evaluation survey align with impact areas of the model as shown in the figure below.

The TSB model was a framework designed to support assessment of clinical and translational research outcomes to measure clinical and community health impacts⁶. The T&E team used the domains of the TSB model to evaluate the impact of the C₂G Program on the potential or demonstrated **clinical, community, economic, and policy benefits of investing in increased access to COVID-19 testing, vaccination, and community-led engagement initiatives in underserved communities (Figure 2)**. The main contribution of the TSB model is its utility in

identifying the core areas where testing outreach and strategies developed through the C₂G program provide clinical, public health, economic and policy benefits.

Figure 2. Translational Science Benefits Model (TSBM)^{2, 6} + Health Equity Impact Areas

<p>CLINICAL</p>	<p>Clinical and Medical Benefits (procedures, guidelines, tools, and products)</p>
<p>COMMUNITY</p>	<p>Community and Public Health Benefits (health activities, care, and promotion)</p>
<p>ECONOMIC</p>	<p>Economic Benefits (commercial products, financial savings, and benefits)</p>
<p>HEALTH EQUITY</p>	<p>Health Equity Benefits* (accessibility, adaptability, reach)</p>
<p>POLICY</p>	<p>Policy and Legislative Benefits (advisory activities, policies, and legislation)</p>

*The TSBM Framework has been adapted for this evaluation to include an indicator for Health Equity benefits.

Most Significant Change. The Most Significant Change (MSC) technique is an evaluation method that involves collecting significant change stories from the field, and having a panel of designated stakeholders select the most significant of these stories³. This reveals program impact and unintended changes and how and when a change came to be. It also helps provide an understanding of the values of different stakeholders. The MSC approach will be incorporated into the post-project follow-up survey. The survey will include an open text question asking respondents to share what they felt was the most significant change that resulted from their project.

III. Results

This evaluation report details the findings from the C₂G 6-month, and 12-month evaluation survey responses and 18-month interviews collected through January 5th, 2024, and analyzed and summarized across projects.

A. Process Evaluation Results

C₂G Program Grant Application Process and Award Utilization

Currently, there are a total of **70 C₂G projects across funding cycles**.

Table 2 shows the number of applications received and awarded during each funding cycle. The number of applicants per cycle has varied, showing an upward trend since cycle two. This trend excluded cycle 6, where there was a slight decline in applications. The funding rate also varied across the cycles and depended upon available funding and the number of quality applications received. The average number of days between award notification and project initiation was calculated from the notice of selection to the first invoice paid out. This variable helped to gauge the timely launch of projects. However, project start dates also varied significantly based on the project teams' ability to submit their documentation promptly.

Table 2. Metrics per C₂G Funding Cycle for the Grant Application Process

C ₂ G Project Cycle	Application Period	Number of Applicants per cycle	Number of Projects Awarded per cycle	Average Number of Days between Award Notification and Project Initiation	Application Funding Rate	% of Awardees that Expended funding in 12-month grant period
Cycle 1	3/3/21 – 5/28/21	31	12	116 days	38.7%	66.7%
Cycle 2	5/7/21 -8/18/21	11	6	93 days	54.5%	66.7%
Cycle 3	7/2/21 -9/30/21	13	5	138 days	38.5%	20%
Cycle 4	10/29/21 – 2/7/22	32	16	122 days	50%	87.5%
Cycle 5	4/1/22 – 7/13/22	43	10	130 days	23.2%	80%
Cycle 6	8/5/22-11/22/22	27	6	106 days	22.2%	83.3%
Cycle 7	3/17/23 - 6/26/23	52	15	89 days	28.8%	--*

**Data not yet available for this cycle*

In this report, evaluation survey data is presented for:

- Cycle 1 n=12 of 12 total projects
- Cycle 2 n = 6 of 6 total projects
- Cycle 3 n = 5 of 5 total projects

- Cycle 4 n= 16 of 16 total projects
- Cycle 5 n= 10 of 10 total projects
- Cycle 6 = 6 of 6 total projects
- Cycle 7 has no data at the time of this report

Satisfaction with CDCC Administration Resources and Support. **Figure 3** summarizes the results from the 6- or 12-month surveys— whichever is the most recent time point —regarding project satisfaction with the application and award process. In this matrix, satisfaction is defined in terms of:

- Overall helpfulness
- Ease of accessing support
- Effectively addressing feedback
- Effectiveness and
- Promptness of support delivery

Overall, projects reported satisfaction with the RADx-UP CDCC administration's support. **Over 85% of respondents were very satisfied or satisfied with each statement** that asked about overall helpfulness. Over **80% of respondents were also very satisfied or satisfied** with the ease of accessing support, CDCC effectively addressing feedback, overall effectiveness. and promptness of support delivery. During interviews, projects reported that they utilized resources on the CDCC website and attended useful meetings throughout their grant period. The social media toolkit was a particularly valuable resource, one project explained:

*"I used several resources, some of the informational flyers for patients, things like that. But **the one that I went to the most and continue to bounce back to every now and then is the social media tool kit** just because I can trust the information, I know it's good and relevant, it's appropriate culturally for multicultural patient populations. It's just good content and so I really appreciate that"* (Project 24_Interview Data).

Figure 3. C₂G Project Satisfaction with CDCC Administration Resources and Support (*n*= 55 projects reporting)
 *Not Applicable responses were not included in the visuals

Satisfaction with the Support Provided by the C₂G Administration Team. Figure 4 summarizes the results from the 6- or 12-month surveys— whichever is the most recent time point —regarding project satisfaction with the application and award process. In this matrix, satisfaction was defined in terms of rating the following as “Very Good” or “Good”:

- Appropriate utilization of communication and dissemination channels
- Communicating available RADx-UP services and resources
- Dissemination of information through RADx-UP communication channels
- Ability to adapt the administrative grant process to meet new and changing needs of projects
- Providing opportunities for C₂G projects to engage in shaping the organizational direction for RADx-UP

Overall, projects reported satisfaction with the support provided by the C₂G administration team. **Over 85% percent of projects rated the C₂G administration team exceptionally well (rated as “Very Good” or “Good”) in regard to communication, use of communication channels, dissemination of information and adapting to meet needs. While 75% rated the team “very good “or “good” in regard to providing opportunities for strategic planning.** Interviews echoed these findings, and projects elaborated that C₂G personnel were very helpful — “I think the **people that we worked with were excellent**. They gave us what we needed, they gave us any suggestions they had, they seemed to be pleased with what we were doing. Those were brief check-ins, but that was appreciated” (Project 13_Interview Data).

Figure 4. C₂G Project Satisfaction with the Support Provided by the C₂G Administration Team (n= 55 projects reporting)

*Not Applicable responses were not included in the visuals

Improvements to CDCC Support and Resources

During interviews, we asked projects to provide suggestions on how the CDCC could improve its support to projects. Most projects did not have any suggestions for CDCC improvements. Project providing feedback suggested simplifying the application process, increasing flexibility in some of the grant requirements, supporting collaboration among projects, and making localized and/or more culturally relevant information available. Increased cross-project collaboration was the most commonly cited suggestion. One project administrator shared,

*"I think for us, **it would have absolutely been helpful to collaborate [with other projects]**, because a lot of this we were figuring out on our own as we went and again, that's perfectly fine, but it would have also been helpful to hear from other organizations. So, I think like maybe check-ins, or if we all come together, or like the regional meetings, but I think **it would have been helpful to hear status updates of other projects**, so we could continue learning and asking questions about some of the challenges we were like facing from time to time" (Project 8_Interview Data).*

B. Outcome Evaluation Results

B1. Sociodemographic Results

Characteristics of C₂G Projects

Geographic Diversity. C₂G funded projects are spread throughout the US, with the majority located in the Southern and Northeastern regions. The C₂G program also addressed gaps in regions where the larger RADx-UP program did not have any or had few funded projects.

The figure below shows the geographic diversity of C₂G projects across the United States (US). The top six states with the highest number of cumulative COVID-19 cases (per 100,000) are Rhode Island, Alaska, Kentucky, North Dakota, and Tennessee⁸. While some of the current funded C₂G projects are in these states, future Covid-19 funding efforts could place more emphasis on funding projects in states where there is an increased COVID-19 incidence and/or mortality rate.

Fig 5: C₂G Project Geographic Diversity

C₂G Project Geographic Diversity (figure developed by the American Institutes for Research (AIR) for RADx-UP)

Organization Type. Figure 6 reflects C₂G project’s organization type on the types of organizations that are funded by the C₂G program. Organizations include medical care, faith based, community centers, coalitions, and public health organizations. There was a total of 55 projects that reported an organization type, and most funded projects were community center/case management organizations.

Figure 6. C₂G Project Organization Type (n= 55 projects reporting)

Underserved Populations Served. Of the 55 projects that reported, all projects (100%) reported serving an underserved population. See [Figure 7](#) for a breakdown of underserved populations represented by C₂G projects. Underserved populations are defined as *populations that the NIH has identified as being underrepresented in biomedical research and known to experience greater morbidity and mortality because of socioeconomic factors*⁹. Survey data show that **C₂G projects have had a wide reach and all populations that fall within underserved populations were reached.** Of the projects that have reported, **socioeconomically disadvantaged, Hispanic/Latino, and Black/African American populations were the underserved populations served most often by C₂G projects.**

Figure 7. C₂G Underserved Populations (n= 55 projects reporting)

*One project can serve more than one underserved population

COVID-19 Vulnerable Communities Served. C₂G projects reached a wide range of COVID-19 vulnerable projects as presented in [Figure 8](#). COVID-19 vulnerable communities are defined as *populations that the NIH has identified as being at greater risk of COVID-19 infection and poor health outcomes from COVID-19*¹⁰. Figure 8 shows that **all communities defined as COVID-19 vulnerable communities have been reached by at least one C₂G project**. Of the projects that reported during this reporting period, **individuals with comorbidities, immigrant communities, and children were the COVID-19 vulnerable communities most often served by C₂G projects**.

Figure 8. C₂G COVID-19 Vulnerable Populations (n= 54 projects reporting)

*One project can serve more than one vulnerable population.

Characteristics of C₂G Projects' Partners. Figure 9 displays the projects' community partner organizations. Projects were asked to indicate if they were collaborating with any organizations, and to list their names. The T&E team then coded this data into themes that represented types of project partners.

Figure 9. Characteristics of C2G Project Partners (n= 49 projects reporting)

*One project can have more than one partner organization

Project Challenges. The T&E team also collected qualitative data on roadblocks or challenges faced by projects at the 6- or 12-month surveys and 18-month interviews. This included challenges to sample collection, challenges to testing, test result reporting, and engaging with community members.

The T&E team then reviewed challenges in the 6-or-12-month surveys and 18-month interviews and coded the responses into several categories. See [Table 3](#) for a list of the codes and examples of corresponding quotes. Fourteen projects reported ongoing and/or resolved challenges. **Of the projects that reported on ongoing challenges experienced, the most common were related to administrative, outreach, and staffing.** *Administrative challenges* were defined as challenges in paperwork, processes, and procurement of non-testing materials. *Outreach challenges* were defined as challenges in establishing channels or engaging in contact with the target population. *Staffing challenges* were challenges related to the inability to hire qualified staff. The 18-month interviews revealed the same types of challenges as those reported in the surveys.

In the surveys, the T&E team also asked projects if challenges were ongoing or resolved. Projects reported testing site challenges and some outreach challenges as resolved. Testing site challenges include challenges related to securing appropriate testing locations.

As challenges were observed, the T&E team communicated them to C₂G leadership so that they could be addressed in a timely manner.

Table 3. Challenges Experienced by Projects from Surveys and Interviews (Survey n= 14 projects reporting; Interviews n = 37)

Code	Challenge Type	Quotes
Administrative	Ongoing	<i>"We are always challenged to find and obtain funding for our services"(Project ID 177_Survey Data).</i>
Outreach	Ongoing & Resolved	<p><i>"Accessing in the rural area was a big problem... Because in Mississippi, the rural areas, a lot of them didn't even have broadband access where you could even do a Zoom where you could get more people. So, it was challenging in a lot of the rural areas to get them the same information about the virus, the vaccine, and the vote. So, we were able to use mobile services to do it. But that was a big challenge serving the rural area." (Project 35_Interview Data)</i></p> <p><i>"There's a fairly high number of undocumented folks in this area and obviously you start trying to survey people and ask questions, people do not-- they don't want to come near you, they don't want to answer anything. So even prior to this funding, when we were doing COVID vaccinations down there, that was an issue because people were very, very nervous about even talking to you." (Project 33_Interview Data)</i></p> <p><i>"In the beginning, there was some resistance to the in house barber facilities and pricing. Through quick thinking and ingenuity, we morphed into a mobile barber FRESH tour, which gave us more flexibility to touch more individuals in environments we controlled." (Project ID 200_Survey Data)</i></p>
Staffing	Ongoing	<p><i>"Lack of personnel numbers needed that were employed during the entire project." (Project ID 194_Survey Data)</i></p> <p><i>"The primary barrier to us not being able to continue it in the way it was before was staffing. So, because of the way that what we do staffing is our primary cost and our primary challenge so when we have the staffing, we can do extra things" (Project 24_Interview Data).</i></p>

Testing Site	Resolved	<i>"Delays were related to cancellation or rescheduling of community events that we could not control. As our community emerges from the pandemic it is clear that organizers such as the city, county, and local non-profits are easing back into large scale community events. Several times we experienced receiving notifications of rescheduling of large events. This was a barrier because we counted on large events to distribute large quantities of testing kits that had expiration dates. We pivoted and leaned on our community partners to distribute testing kits." (Project ID 18o_Survey Data)</i>

B2. C₂G Project Outcomes and Impacts

C₂G Testing and Enrollment, Project Activities, and Products Developed

One of the C₂G program aims was to increase training, education, communication, information dissemination, and capacity building related to COVID-19 testing, isolation, and contact tracing in communities. Of the 53 projects that reported in the 6- or -12-month surveys — **(79%) were engaging their community in testing**. Additionally, **an estimated 120,000 people had been reached through C₂G project testing efforts**. It is important to note that this is an estimate. Projects are asked in their 12-month evaluation survey to report an estimate for the number of people reached through testing efforts — some projects reported number of tests distributed rather than people reached, and some people may have received more than one test.

Surveys gathered information about the types of activities C₂G projects engaged in; **Figure 10** illustrates the wide range of these activities. **Across all six cycles, generating communication materials for COVID-19 testing, and training and education** were the most common project activities. The 18-month interviews provided additional context on communicating testing, **and they revealed that** projects encouraged testing via face-to-face recruitment strategies and engaged trusted community members and organizations to facilitate testing. Moreover, C₂G projects highlighted the importance of clearly communicating testing availability to communities:

*"We found that **consistent communication about our [testing] schedule was key**. So we posted weekly on our social media platforms a very routine schedule. We had our hours, our location. And then as testing recommendations changed, or any sort of update related to testing was going on, we could include that there as well weekly" (Project 28_Interview Data).*

Surveys indicated that 45 out of 54 projects that reported (83%) provided training or education to their community around COVID-19 testing projects. Some examples of training included outreach to community members, homeless shelters, community health workers, and community leaders via educational sessions, town halls.

Figure 10. C2G Project Activities (n= 54 projects reporting).

*One project can have more than one activity. Category ‘Other’ is not included in the visual.

Forty-six out of 54 (85%) projects reported that they developed and disseminated COVID-19 testing communication materials. Examples include handouts and culturally/linguistically appropriate materials distributed around the community, at outreach events, posted on social media, and shared at testing events. In the 6- and 12-month surveys, projects described their education activities:

“We provided in house information distribution and town halls for education. We also provided education to community members while distributing kits.” (Project ID 195_Survey Data).

“Students engaged with community members at events and developed materials based on community concerns, information provided by the state Health Department, CDC, and RADx-Up monthly meetings.” (Project ID 204_Survey Data).

Eighteen-month interviews revealed that creating culturally relevant educational materials and working with other community partners was especially important for disseminating education materials:

“Our project involved immigrants, non-English speakers generally, and those impacted by incarceration. Generally, neighbors from low-income backgrounds. We really focused on creating linguistically and culturally responsive education and then finding creative

ways throughout the pandemic to get that out there right. Door-to-door canvassing... *Working alongside community organizations, whether t'at's other local nonprofits, faith-based organizations, informal groups of folks, schools, and so on and so forth. Connecting our neighbors with existing opportunities to get vaccinated and tested and then helping organize community-led walk-ins and conversations.*" (Project 32_Interview Data).

In their 12-month surveys, projects were asked to report if they had developed any products (community event, publication, grant proposal or conference presentation), with results reported in **Figure 11**. Twenty-nine projects reported that that they had developed products, with the majority being community events.

Figure 11. C₂G Research Products Developed (n= 29 projects reporting)

*One project can have more than one Research Product. Category 'Other' is not included in the visual.

IV. Key Takeaways and Conclusion

C₂G projects advanced COVID-19 testing research by improving access to and uptake of COVID-19 testing in communities of underserved and vulnerable populations across the United States. There were 70 C₂G projects across 7 funding cycles reflecting diverse geographic settings and serving racial minorities and socioeconomically disadvantaged populations. The vulnerable populations most commonly supported by C₂G projects included individuals with comorbidities, immigrant communities, and children.

By funding innovative and diverse community collaboration grants, the RADxUP consortium was able to identify and address barriers and facilitators to effective testing and to implement testing programs within underserved communities. Through effective grant administration

and research support, the CDCC also helped awardees achieve their implementation goals (COVID-19 awareness, testing and community engagement).

Most projects reported developing COVID-19 testing materials and training and education. There was an emphasis on the need for culturally appropriate materials, one-on-one recruitment strategies, and engagement of community members in implementation strategies. Especially because C₂G projects were short-term (i.e. 12 months), engagement of the community was pivotal to the successful implementation. Research partnerships developed through the C₂G awards increased awardees' capacity to engage in future research and established a research infrastructure that may be available to future research consortiums.

Projects also identified challenges with grant administration processes, target population engagement (outreach) and hiring qualified staff (staffing). Suggested improvements to administrative support include simplifying the grant application process, increasing flexibility in grant requirements, supporting collaboration among projects, and making localized and/or more culturally relevant information available. Also, a later report on staffing challenges may be due to poor salaries and benefits for these short-term projects; funding agencies can consider higher salaries and benefits combined with more stable, long-term funding.

Next steps for evaluation reporting to the end of the C₂G program.

The T&E team will continue to:

1. Monitor C₂G program progress through the 6-month and 12-month surveys and develop impact profiles and annual report.
2. Towards the end of the C₂G program, the T&E team will support the development of a summative evaluation report.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. RADx-UP C2G Evaluation Logic Model

Community Collaboration Mini-Grant Evaluation Logic Model

